

Field programmable gate array implementation of multiwavelet transform based orthogonal frequency division multiplexing system

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ABSTRACT

This article offers an efficient design and implementation of a discrete multiwavelet critical-sampling transform based orthogonal frequency division multiplexing (DMWCST-OFDM) transceiver using field programmable gate array (FPGA) platform. The design uses 16-point discrete multiwavelet critical-sampling transform (DMWCST) and its inverse as main processing modules. All modules were designed using a part of Vivado® Design Suite version (2015.2), which is Xilinx system generator (XSG), and is compatible with MATLAB Simulink version R2013b. The FPGA implementation is carried out on a Zynq (XC7Z020-1CLG484) evaluation board with joint test action group (JTAG) hardware co-simulation. According to the results obtained from the implementation tools, the implemented system is efficient in terms of resource utilization and could support the real-time operations.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Orthogonal frequency division multiplexing (OFDM) divides the available spectrum into several parallel subcarriers. Each one of these subcarriers is modulated by a data stream with low rate at different orthogonal carrier frequency [1]–[3]. In the traditional OFDM systems, the fast Fourier transform (FFT) is used for fulfilling the requirement of orthogonality between the different subcarriers [4]–[8]. FFT has a major drawback arising from using rectangular window, which creates high side lobes in the transmitting signals, thereby increase sensitivity of the OFDM system to the Inter-Carrier Interference (ICI) and a low system performance [9]–[14]. Discrete multiwavelet critical-sampling transform based OFDM system (DMWCST-OFDM) was proposed to mitigate the impairments of FFT based OFDM system [15]–[20]. In the proposed design, an inverse discrete multiwavelet critical-sampling transform (IDMWCST) and DMWCST are used in the realization of the OFDM system instead of inverse fast Fourier transform (IFFT) and FFT, respectively.

Real-time implementation for OFDM systems plays a major role in next generation communication systems. Field programmable gate array (FPGA) give us a good solution in term of high-performance and low-cost to implement and verify the digital communication systems. Since, FPGA has high flexibility and can be upgraded continuously, it has become widely relied upon to implement digital signal processing (DSP) functions [21]–[24]. Veena and Swamy [25] presented the FPGA implementation of discrete multiwavelet over-sampling transform (DMWOST) for OFDM using Xilinx integrated synthesis environment (Xilinx ISE) targeting Virtex-5 FPGA. It was found that the DWMOST required 2695 slices and

51 mW power dissipation. On the other hand, DWMOST gives poor bit error rate performance as compared by DMWCST [20] will be presented in this work. While [26], offered the modified DMWOST architecture. Which was implemented on VirtexII FPGA and operates at 300 MHz frequency. The architecture occupied area of less than 1%, with consumed power of 28 mW.

The aim of this paper is to present the design and implementation of the DMWCST-OFDM system at real-time using FPGA platform. The presented system has been built using a high-level design tool which is a part of Vivado[®] Design Suite called Xilinx system generator (XSG). XSG comes with a predefined Xilinx blockset along with MATLAB Simulink software, and can be used to implement the algorithms, and mapped directly into target FPGA hardware. MATLAB's Simulink enables the designer to use high-level abstractions of the system that can be automatically compiled into FPGA. It provides the designer a thin boundary between hardware and software, given that it enables to design the hardware by allowing to synthesize the blocks into very high-speed integrated circuit hardware description language (VHDL) and compiling them into FPGA with a single click.

The rest of the paper is organized in the following order. An overview of the DMWCST-OFDM system is detailed in section 2. Section 3 presents the implementation of the DMWCST-OFDM system on FPGA using XSG. Section 4 discusses the results, and the conclusions are presented in section 5.

2. THE ORETICAL BASIS

The block diagram of DMWCST-OFDM system is illustrated in Figure 1. At the transmitter side, a serial-binary data is generated randomly. The serial-to-parallel (S/P) conversion converts serial bit stream into parallel lower data sub-streams, which then formatted into symbols required for transmission. After that, each symbol is mapped according to the quadrature phase shift keying (QPSK) mapping technique, resulting in N_c sub-channels. Then, several of null-subcarriers are added to the resulted data sequences. N_f -point IDMCST is applied to the signal in order to achieve orthogonality between subcarriers. Finally, the data are sent to the receiver after being converted to a frame structure. The design of the receiver consists of the inverse operations of the transmitter side. These operations are performed in a reverse order to yield the correct data stream [20].

Figure 1. Block diagram of the DMWCST-OFDM

3. METHOD

The DMWCST-OFDM system has been implemented by utilizing the parallelization capabilities of the FPGA in order to decrease the latency and get the final output from the design. Moreover, pipeline options available in the Xilinx blocks are exploited. The tools employed in this work are MATLAB R2013b-64 bit along with Simulink 8.2 and Vivado[®] Design Suite version 2015.2. The number of used subcarrier (N_f) in this implementation is 16, while the number of useful subcarrier (N_c) is 12. The implementation of DMWCST-OFDM system consists of two parts: the transmitter and the receiver. The details of each part are presented in the following sub-sections.

3.1. Transmitter section

The first block in the transmitter side is S/P and mapping, the XSG implementation of this block is illustrated in Figure 2. The S/P block takes the serial unsigned data represented in the fixed point of one bit with zero binary point, and it produces a single output of two consequential input bits to be mapped to the corresponding QPSK symbol. The most significant word first is used to arrange the serial input data. The fact that the clock frequency reduces by half after S/P block needs to be taken into consideration. Then, the two bits have been separated into select signal for two multiplexers by using two slices in order to decide the I (In phase) and Q (Quadrature phase) values of the desired complex symbol.

Figure 2. XSG model of the S/P and mapping

Then a set of null subcarriers are inserted to each OFDM symbol. The Xilinx implementation of this block is depicted in Figure 3. Two zeros are added at the beginning and the end of each OFDM symbol. An unsigned fixed-point representation is used to represent a zero value as the output of the constant block. The set of the multiplexers have been used to allocate the OFDM symbol and control the flow of the input to the next subsystem. They are controlled by the M-code and counter. The delay blocks at the input of the multiplexers are used to make each I or Q sample of one OFDM symbol enter the intended multiplexer simultaneously, which is the time of the last sample in that OFDM symbol. The zero constant block is also utilized to reset the multiplexers between the OFDM symbols.

Figure 3. XSG model of the zero padding

The XSG implementation of IDMWCST, which is achieved by matrix multiplication as given in [20], consists of many blocks; one of them is used to perform all the multiplication processes required through the matrix multiplication, while the other blocks are used to perform the addition processes between the multiplication processes. Each element of the output will be the results of the addition blocks. In order to make the design to require less resources, all multiplication and addition processes with zero coefficients are not taken into consideration. The XSG implementation of addition blocks are presented in Figure 4.

Finally, Figure 5 shows the implementation architecture of the P/S converter. Where, the incoming parallel I and Q data are converted to one serial sequence by the time division multiplexer. Then two multiplexers are used to separate the I and Q data for simultaneous transmission.

Figure 4. XSG implementation of addition blocks

Figure 5. XSG model of P/S converter

3.2. Receiver section

The first step in the receiver side is convert the I and Q components from serial to parallel by S/P converter. The Xilinx implementation of this step is depicted in Figure 6. The multiplexer is used to control the input flow, at the first 16 clocks, which is equal to period of the OFDM symbol, the I data will be passed to the time division demultiplexer, then at the second 16 clocks, the Q data will be passed. The time division demultiplexer will convert the I and Q components from serial to parallel.

The second step is performing DMWCST. The XSG implementation of this block is also can be achieved by matrix multiplication between the transformation matrix given in [20], and the input vector of the I and Q. (Same as in the transmitter side the zero coefficients are not taken into the consideration).

After that, the implementation architecture of the remove zero padding block is achieved as in Figure 7. There are two purposes for designing this block. The first is to remove the null subcarriers from each OFDM symbol, and the second is to compel the I and Q components to pass to next block simultaneously, because the I and Q components prior to this subsystem was passing sequentially. The

terminator blocks are utilized to remove the null subcarriers, which were added at the beginning and end of the OFDM symbol at the transmitter side. Then two multiplexers with delay blocks are used to separate the I and Q component to compel them to pass through the next subsystem simultaneously, which are controlled by the counter and the M-code.

Figure 6. XSG model of the S/P converter

Figure 7. XSG model of the remove zero padding

Finally, the hard decision method is used to perform the QPSK demapping. First, the I and Q values are compared with a threshold of value 0. Then, the decisions are grouped through the concat block to configure a 2-bit QPSK symbol. Next, the QPSK symbol is converted to binary data using a P/S conversion block. The XSG implementation module of this step is presented in Figure 8.

Figure 8. XSG model of the de-mapping and P/S converter

4. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Figure 9 shows a hardware co-simulation model for the OFDM-DMWCST system and its programming to Zynq (XC7Z020-1CLG484) FPGA board. It uses a joint test action group (JTAG) connection. The VHDL codes are generated after the co-simulation. From this figure, it is clear that the output from the hardware co-simulation model matches the input data. So, the programming of the FPGA board has been successful.

The VHDL coding of the system is accomplished through the hardware co-simulation process. The generated VHDL codes are imported into the Vivado tool for analysis at the register transfer level (RTL), where synthesis and implementation operations are performed. These operations will produce a large number of reports. The reports describe concerns regarding the implementation processes such as storage resources required, I/O resources required, and power required.

Figure 9. Hardware co-simulation for the OFDM-DMWCST

Tables 1 and 2 give a brief description of the area results in the context of resource consumption for the transmitter and receiver of the Xilinx OFDM-DMWCST, respectively. From these figures, it is noticed that the design is efficient in terms of resource utilization. Finally, summery results of the proposed OFDM-

DMWCST model are compared with the reference design [25], [26]. The comparison results are reported in Table 3. Table 3 indicates that our Xilinx design consumes little power compared with the total power of the board. Where, the transmitter consumes 12 mW, which is equal to half the amount of power consumed by the reference [25].

Table 1. Area of utilization report for the transmitter

Resource	Utilization	Available	Utilization (%)
FF	276	106400	0.26
LUT	3441	53200	6.47
Memory LUT	86	17400	0.49
I/O	26	200	13.00
BUFG	1	32	3.12

Table 2. Area of utilization report for the receiver

Resource	Utilization	Available	Utilization (%)
FF	700	106400	0.66
LUT	3363	53200	6.32
Memory LUT	116	17400	0.67
I/O	26	200	13.00
BUFG	1	32	3.12

From the above results, it is clearly that the design consumes less than 1% resources and low power. The design gave a better performance for its latency and throughput by designing a parallel and pipelined architecture for the proposed model compared with [25], [26]. So, the proposed design is suitable for real time and low power applications.

Table 3. Summary results reports compared with references [25], [26]

Parameter	References [25]	References [26]	Proposed design
FF	1996	72	700
Memory LUT	---	126	116
I/O	---	64	26
BUFG	---	1	1
Power Dissipation	24 mW	---	12 mW

5. CONCLUSION

A baseband OFDM-DMWCST system was designed and successfully implemented on Zynq (XC7Z020-1CLG484) FPGA board using XSG tool, which is a part of Vivado® Design Suite software. XSG combined with MATLAB/Simulink provided an easier and efficient way of implementing the OFDM-DMWCST on FPGA. Also, the hardware co-simulation feature of the XSG software paved the way for an easier approach in testing and debugging the system effectively at real-time. The hardware simulation and synthesis results showed that the implemented system is correctly working, efficient in terms of resource utilization, and supports real-time operations.

As, the literature referred presented the FPGA implementation of DMWCST based OFDM, where focused on implementation of the transform only and not implement the OFDM as a complete system compared with our work. In our work a new implementation of DMWCST based OFDM is designed and synthesized. So, the results obtained are considered as reference design for DMWCST based OFDM architecture on FPGA.

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